

Descrição de Siglas		
ID	Título	Referência
TP03	Comparative Analysis of Machine Learning Algorithms for Prediction of PCOS	Chauhan, P., Patil, P., Rane, N., Raundale, P., & Kanakia, H. (2021, June). Comparative analysis of machine learning algorithms for prediction of pcos. In 2021 international conference on communication information and computing technology (ICCICT) (pp. 1-7). IEEE.
TP04	A Novel Approach for Polycystic Ovary Syndrome Prediction Using Machine Learning in Bioinformatics	Nasim, S., Almutairi, M. S., Munir, K., Raza, A., & Younas, F. (2022). A novel approach for polycystic ovary syndrome prediction using machine learning in bioinformatics. IEEE Access, 10, 97610-97624.
TP05	Hybrid Machine Learning Model for Early Discovery and Prediction of Polycystic Ovary Syndrome	Swamy, S. R., & KS, N. P. (2022, December). Hybrid machine learning model for early discovery and prediction of polycystic ovary syndrome. In 2022 Second International Conference on Advanced Technologies in Intelligent Control, Environment, Computing & Communication Engineering (ICATIECE) (pp. 1-8). IEEE.
TP06	SPOSDS: A smart Polycystic Ovary Syndrome diagnostic system using machine learning	Tiwari, S., Kane, L., Koundal, D., Jain, A., Alhudaif, A., Polat, K., ... & Althubiti, S. A. (2022). SPOSDS: A smart Polycystic Ovary Syndrome diagnostic system using machine learning. Expert Systems with Applications, 203, 117592.
TP07	Raman spectroscopy of follicular fluid and plasma with machine-learning algorithms for polycystic ovary syndrome screening	Zhang, X., Liang, B., Zhang, J., Hao, X., Xu, X., Chang, H. M., ... & Tan, J. (2021). Raman spectroscopy of follicular fluid and plasma with machine-learning algorithms for polycystic ovary syndrome screening. Molecular and cellular endocrinology, 523, 111139.
TP08	SmS: SMOTE-stacked hybrid model for diagnosis of polycystic ovary syndrome using feature selection method	Kumari, R., Singh, J., & Gosain, A. (2023). SmS: SMOTE-stacked hybrid model for diagnosis of polycystic ovary syndrome using feature selection method. Expert Systems with Applications, 225, 120102.
TP10	Early identification of PCOS with commonly known diseases: Obesity, diabetes, high blood pressure and heart disease using machine learning techniques	Aggarwal, S., & Pandey, K. (2023). Early identification of PCOS with commonly known diseases: Obesity, diabetes, high blood pressure and heart disease using machine learning techniques. Expert Systems with Applications, 217, 119532.
TP11	Detection of polycystic ovarian syndrome using follicle recognition technique	Rachana, B., Priyanka, T., Sahana, K. N., Supriya, T. R., Parameshachari, B. D., & Sunitha, R. (2021). Detection of polycystic ovarian syndrome using follicle recognition technique. Global Transitions Proceedings, 2(2), 304-308.
TP12	A clinical decision support system for polycystic ovarian syndrome using red deer algorithm and random forest classifier	Sreejith, S., Nehemiah, H. K., & Kannan, A. (2022). A clinical decision support system for polycystic ovarian syndrome using red deer algorithm and random forest classifier. Healthcare Analytics, 2, 100102.
TP17	Dysregulated immunological and metabolic functions discovered by a polygenic integrative analysis for PCOS	Ho, C. H., Chang, C. M., Li, H. Y., Shen, H. Y., Lieu, F. K., & Wang, P. S. G. (2020). Dysregulated immunological and metabolic functions discovered by a polygenic integrative analysis for PCOS. Reproductive BioMedicine Online, 40(1), 160-167.
TP114	Polycystic ovary syndrome: clinical and laboratory variables related to new phenotypes using machine-learning models	Silva, I. S., Ferreira, C. N., Costa, L. B. X., Sóter, M. O., Carvalho, L. M. L., de C. Albuquerque, J., ... & Gomes, K. B. (2022). Polycystic ovary syndrome: clinical and laboratory variables related to new phenotypes using machine-learning models. Journal of Endocrinological Investigation, 1-9.
TP115	An extended machine learning technique for polycystic ovary syndrome detection using ovary ultrasound image	Suha, S. A., & Islam, M. N. (2022). An extended machine learning technique for polycystic ovary syndrome detection using ovary ultrasound image. Scientific Reports, 12(1), 17123.
TP116	Machine-Aided Self-diagnostic Prediction Models for Polycystic Ovary Syndrome: Observational Study	Zigarelli, A., Jia, Z., & Lee, H. (2022). Machine-aided self-diagnostic prediction models for polycystic ovary syndrome: observational study. JMIR Formative Research, 6(3), e29967.
TP117	Exploring the dominant features and data-driven detection of polycystic ovary syndrome through modified stacking ensemble machine learning technique	Suha, S. A., & Islam, M. N. (2023). Exploring the dominant features and data-driven detection of polycystic ovary syndrome through modified stacking ensemble machine learning technique. Heliyon, 9(3).
TP118	A new model for predicting the occurrence of polycystic ovary syndrome: Based on data of tongue and pulse	Wang, W., Zeng, W., He, S., Shi, Y., Chen, X., Tu, L., ... & Yin, X. (2023). A new model for predicting the occurrence of polycystic ovary syndrome: Based on data of tongue and pulse. Digital health, 9, 20552076231160323.
TP120	Prediction of PCOS and Mental Health Using Fuzzy Inference and SVM	Kodipalli, A., & Devi, S. (2021). Prediction of PCOS and mental health using fuzzy inference and SVM. Frontiers in public health, 9, 789569.

Aplicação de CI e CE nos trabalhos primários			
Base de Dados	Trabalhos selecionados	Trabalhos incluídos	ID
Scopus	2	0	-
ScienceDirect	108	8	TP06, TP07, TP08, TP10, TP11, TP12, TP17 e TP41
IEEE Xplore	4	3	TP03, TP04, TP05
MEDLINE/PubMed (via National Library of Medicine)	10	7	TP114, TP115, TP116, TP117, TP118, 119 e TP120
Total	124	18	-

Catálogo de estudios primários		
ID	Título	Base
TP03	Comparative Analysis of Machine Learning Algorithms for Prediction of PCOS	IEEE Xplore
TP04	A Novel Approach for Polycystic Ovary Syndrome Prediction Using Machine Learning in Bioinformatics	IEEE Xplore
TP05	Hybrid Machine Learning Model for Early Discovery and Prediction of Polycystic Ovary Syndrome	IEEE Xplore
TP06	SPOSDS: A smart Polycystic Ovary Syndrome diagnostic system using machine learning	ScienceDirect
TP07	Raman spectroscopy of follicular fluid and plasma with machine-learning algorithms for polycystic ovary syndrome screening	ScienceDirect
TP08	SmS: SMOTE-stacked hybrid model for diagnosis of polycystic ovary syndrome using feature selection method	ScienceDirect
TP10	Early identification of PCOS with commonly known diseases: Obesity, diabetes, high blood pressure and heart disease using machine learning techniques	ScienceDirect
TP11	Detection of polycystic ovarian syndrome using follicle recognition technique	ScienceDirect
TP12	A clinical decision support system for polycystic ovarian syndrome using red deer algorithm and random forest classifier	ScienceDirect
TP17	Dysregulated immunological and metabolic functions discovered by a polygenic integrative analysis for PCOS	ScienceDirect
TP41	Food Image-based diet recommendation framework to overcome PCOS problem in women using deep convolutional neural network	ScienceDirect

TP114	Polycystic ovary syndrome: clinical and laboratory variables related to new phenotypes using machine-learning models	MEDLINE/PubMed (via National Library of Medicine)
TP115	An extended machine learning technique for polycystic ovary syndrome detection using ovary ultrasound image	MEDLINE/PubMed (via National Library of Medicine)
TP116	Machine-Aided Self-diagnostic Prediction Models for Polycystic Ovary Syndrome: Observational Study	MEDLINE/PubMed (via National Library of Medicine)
TP117	Exploring the dominant features and data-driven detection of polycystic ovary syndrome through modified stacking ensemble machine learning technique	MEDLINE/PubMed (via National Library of Medicine)
TP118	A new model for predicting the occurrence of polycystic ovary syndrome: Based on data of tongue and pulse	MEDLINE/PubMed (via National Library of Medicine)
TP119	Predicting polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) with machine learning algorithms from electronic health records	MEDLINE/PubMed (via National Library of Medicine)
TP120	Prediction of PCOS and Mental Health Using Fuzzy Inference and SVM	MEDLINE/PubMed (via National Library of Medicine)

Qualidade total por trabalho		
ID	Título	Pontuação
TP05	Hybrid Machine Learning Model for Early Discovery and Prediction of Polycystic Ovary Syndrome	5
TP08	SmS: SMOTE-stacked hybrid model for diagnosis of polycystic ovary syndrome using feature selection method	5
TP10	Early identification of PCOS with commonly known diseases: Obesity, diabetes, high blood pressure and heart disease using machine learning techniques	5
TP12	A clinical decision support system for polycystic ovarian syndrome using red deer algorithm and random forest classifier	5
TP115	An extended machine learning technique for polycystic ovary syndrome detection using ovary ultrasound image	5
TP117	Exploring the dominant features and data-driven detection of polycystic ovary syndrome through modified stacking ensemble machine learning technique	5
TP03	Comparative Analysis of Machine Learning Algorithms for Prediction of PCOS	4,5
TP06	SPOSDS: A smart Polycystic Ovary Syndrome diagnostic system using machine learning	4,5
TP11	Detection of polycystic ovarian syndrome using follicle recognition technique	4,5
TP118	A new model for predicting the occurrence of polycystic ovary syndrome: Based on data of tongue and pulse	4
TP120	Prediction of PCOS and Mental Health Using Fuzzy Inference and SVM	4
TP04	A Novel Approach for Polycystic Ovary Syndrome Prediction Using Machine Learning in Bioinformatics	3,5
TP114	Polycystic ovary syndrome: clinical and laboratory variables related to new phenotypes using machine-learning models	3,5
TP07	Raman spectroscopy of follicular fluid and plasma with machine-learning algorithms for polycystic ovary syndrome screening	3

TP116	Machine-Aided Self-diagnostic Prediction Models for Polycystic Ovary Syndrome: Observational Study	3
TP17	Dysregulated immunological and metabolic functions discovered by a polygenic integrative analysis for PCOS	1,5

Critérios de qualidade						
ID	O trabalho é validado com dados reais?	Está claro qual(is) técnica(s) foi(ram) utilizada(s) no trabalho?	O trabalho mostra algum desafio quanto ao uso de técnicas de machine learning no diagnóstico da SOP?	O trabalho mostra alguma característica da mulher que foi usada para a extração de critérios para a detecção de SOP?	O trabalho apresentado tem resultados relevantes para a pesquisa?	NOTA
TP03	1	1	0,5	1	1	4,5
TP04	1	1	0	1	0,5	3,5
TP05	0,5	1	0	1	1	5
TP06	1	1	1	1	0,5	4,5
TP07	1	1	0	1	0	3
TP08	1	1	1	1	1	5
TP10	1	1	0	1	1	5
TP11	1	1	1	1	0,5	4,5
TP12	1	1	1	1	1	5
TP114	1	1	0	1	0,5	3,5
TP115	1	1	1	1	1	5
TP116	1	1	0	1	0	3
TP117	1	1	1	1	1	5
TP118	1	1	0	1	1	4
TP120	1	1	0	1	1	4

Legenda	
Descrição	Nota
Sim (S)	1
Não (N)	0
Parcialmente (P)	0,5

Notas totais calculadas para cada Critério de Qualidade	
CQ1	14,5
CQ2	15
CQ3	6,5
CQ4	15
CQ5	11

Ano de Publicação	
ID	Ano
TP03	2021
TP04	2022
TP05	2022
TP06	2022
TP07	2021
TP08	2023
TP10	2023
TP11	2021
TP12	2022
TP114	2021
TP115	2022
TP116	2022
TP117	2023
TP118	2023
TP120	2021

Ano de Publicação	
Ano	Quantidade de trabalhos
2021	5
2022	6
2023	4

Técnicas utilizadas		
Técnica	Número de repetições	ID
Support Vector Machine	11	TP03, TP04, TP06, TP08, TP10, TP11, TP12, TP115, TP117, TP118 e TP120
K-Nearest Neighbor	10	TP03, TP05, TP06, TP07, TP10, TP11, TP12, TP115, TP117 e TP120
Decision Tree	10	TP03, TP05, TP06, TP08, TP10, TP11, TP12, TP115, TP117 e TP120
Random Forest	9	TP04, TP05, TP06, TP07, TP08, TP10, TP114, TP115 e TP117
Logistic Regression	9	TP03, TP04, TP05, TP06, TP08, TP10, TP12, TP115 e TP117
Categorical Gradient Boosting	8	TP04, TP05, TP06, TP07, TP10, TP115, TP116, e TP117
Naive Bayes	7	TP03, TP08, TP11, TP12, TP115, TP117 e TP120
Gradient Boosting	7	TP04, TP05, TP06, TP10, TP115, TP117 e TP118
Extreme Gradient Boosting	5	TP06, TP07, TP115, TP117 e TP118
Adaptive Boosting	4	TP06, TP08, TP115 e TP117
K-mean	3	TP10, TP114 e TP116
Multilayer Perceptron	2	TP04 e TP118
Stochastic Gradient Descent	1	TP04
Linear Regression	1	TP04
Bayesian Ridge	1	TP04
Gaussian Naive Bayes	1	TP04
Extreme Gradient Boosting with Random Forest	1	TP05
Hybrid Classifier	1	TP05
Linear Discriminant Analysis	1	TP06
Quadratic Discriminant Analysis	1	TP06
Stacking	1	TP07
Stacking Logistic Regression	1	TP08
Stacking Support Vector Machine	1	TP08
Stacking Decision Tree	1	TP08
Stacking Random Forest	1	TP08
Stacking Naive Bayes	1	TP08
Stacking Adaptive Boosting	1	TP08
Hybrid Random Forest and Logistic Regression	1	TP10
Método proposto	1	TP12
Convolutional Neural Network	1	TP115
Stochastic Gradient Descent	1	TP04

Técnicas com melhor desempenho		
Técnica	Número de repetições	ID
Random Forest	4	TP06, TP08, TP12, TP114
Support Vector Machine	2	TP118, TP120
Gradient Boosting	2	TP117, TP10
K-Nearest Neighbor	1	TP11
Decision Tree	1	TP03
Gaussian Naive Bayes	1	TP04
Extreme Gradient Boosting with Random Forest	1	TP115
Hybrid	1	TP05
Stacking Adaptive Boosting	1	TP08

Métricas utilizadas		
Métrica	Número de repetições	ID
Accuracy	14	TP03, TP04, TP05, TP06, TP07, TP08, TP10, TP11, TP12, TP115, TP116, TP177, TP118 e TP120
Recall	13	TP03, TP04, TP05, TP06, TP07, TP08, TP10, TP12, TP114, TP115, TP116, TP117 e TP118
Precision	8	TP03, TP04, TP06, TP08, TP10, TP115, TP116 e TP117
F1-Score	8	TP03, TP04, TP05, TP08, TP10, TP115, TP116 e TP117
Specificity	4	TP03, TP07, TP12 e TP118
ROC	2	TP114 e TP115
Error	1	TP05
AUC	1	TP05
F-score	1	TP06
Execution time	1	TP115
Training time	1	TP04

Dificuldades relatadas nos trabalhos		
Desafios	Número de repetições	ID
Dados ruidosos	3	TP03, TP12 e TP117
Seleção de recursos	2	TP05 e TP06
Dados discrepantes	2	TP03 e TP12
Dados desorganizados	1	TP03
Dados ausentes	1	TP03
Dados desequilibrados	1	TP117
Dados duplicados	1	TP03
Implementação dado um grande conjunto de dados	1	TP117
Conjunto de dados pequeno	1	TP117
Alta complexidade computacional	1	TP05
A técnica Logist Regression é suscetível a dados sobreajustados e inadequado para distribuição não linear	1	TP08
SVM é uma técnica que é computacionalmente cara e possui um alto tempo de treinamento	1	TP08
Decision Tree é um algoritmo cuja divisão de nós é muito complexa e inadequada para conjunto de dados onde as informações são insuficientes	1	TP08
Random Forest é uma técnica que gera diversas árvores, aumentando o tempo de treinamento do modelo	1	TP08
Naive Bayes é um algoritmo que ao lidar com grandes conjuntos de dados, torna-se difícil de implementar	1	TP08
Adaptative Boosting é uma técnica que requer um conjunto de dados de alta qualidade, sem discrepâncias e ruídos	1	TP08
A técnica Decision Tree tem a precisão frequentemente alterada porque uma pequena mudança no tamanho dos dados pode levar a uma grande mudança na estrutura de uma decisão ótima	1	TP10
No algoritmo k-Nearest Neighbors a pontuação de treinamento e a precisão da pontuação de validação cruzada mudam continuamente e fornece menos precisão em comparação com todos os cinco algoritmos de classificação pela razão que esta técnica não funciona bem com grandes conjuntos de dados	1	TP10
Na técnica Support Vector Machine a curva de aprendizado indica que a pontuação de treinamento e a pontuação de validação cruzada variam muito, pois esta técnica não funciona bem quando temos um grande conjunto de dados porque o treinamento necessário o tempo é maior	1	TP10
A limitação do algoritmo KNN ao ser usado para a previsão de SOP foi o tempo computacional	1	TP11
As limitações dos modelos de aprendizagem profunda são que eles são caros para treinar e exigem muito tempo e poder de processamento	1	TP115
Os algoritmos convencionais de aprendizado de máquina podem falhar ao trabalhar com muitos atributos e mecanismos subjacentes de dados complicados, como dados desequilibrados, de alta dimensão, ruidosos e assim por diante.	1	TP117

Características da mulher		
Características	Número de repetições	ID
Idade	12	TP04, TP05, TP06, TP07, TP08, TP10, TP12, TP114, TP116, TP117, TP118 e TP120
IMC	9	TP04, TP06, TP08, TP10, TP12, TP114, TP116, TP117 e TP118
Perda de Cabelo	8	TP03, TP04, TP06, TP08, TP12, TP116, TP117 e TP120
Peso	8	TP04, TP06, TP05, TP08, TP12, TP116, TP117 e TP118
FSH	8	TP04, TP05, TP07, TP08, TP12, TP114, TP116 e TP117
Ciclo	8	TP03, TP04, TP06, TP08, TP12, TP116, TP117 e TP120
Duração do ciclo	8	TP03, TP04, TP06, TP08, TP12, TP116, TP117 e TP120
Ganho ou perda de peso	8	TP03, TP04, TP06, TP08, TP12, TP116, TP117 e TP120
LH	7	TP04, TP05, TP07, TP08, TP12, TP116 e TP117
Exercício físico	6	TP03, TP06, TP08, TP12, TP116 e TP117
Fast food	6	TP04, TP06, TP08, TP12, TP116 e TP117
Altura	6	TP06, TP08, TP12, TP116, TP117 e TP118
Vit D3	5	TP04, TP08, TP12, TP116 e TP117
AMH	5	TP04, TP08, TP12, TP116 e TP117
Escurecimento da pele	5	TP04, TP06, TP08, TP12 e TP117
Gravidez	5	TP06, TP08, TP12, TP116 e TP117
PRG	5	TP04, TP08, TP12, TP116 e TP117
Quadril	5	TP06, TP08, TP12, TP116 e TP117
Cintura	5	TP06, TP08, TP12, TP116 e TP117
Pressão arterial sistólica	5	TP06, TP08, TP12, TP116 e TP117
Ganho de Peso	5	TP06, TP08, TP12, TP116 e TP117
Número de aborto	4	TP06, TP08, TP116 e TP117
Glicemia	4	TP07, TP10, TP114 e TP116
Crescimento de cabelo	4	TP04, TP08, TP12 e TP117
SOP	4	TP05, TP08, TP12 e TP114
Pressão arterial diastólica	4	TP06, TP08, TP12 e TP116
Folículo L	4	TP04, TP08, TP12 e TP117
Folículo R	4	TP04, TP08, TP12 e TP117
Média tamanho folículo L	4	TP08, TP12, TP116 e TP117
Média tamanho folículo R	4	TP08, TP12, TP116 e TP117
TSH	4	TP05, TP08, TP12 e TP117
Endométrio	4	TP08, TP12, TP116 e TP117
FSH/LH	3	TP04, TP12 e TP117
HB	3	TP08, TP12 e TP117
PRL	3	TP08, TP12 e TP116
Frequência cardíaca	3	TP06, TP12 e TP117
RBS	3	TP08, TP12 e TP117
Estado civil	2	TP04 e TP12

20 Características da mulher mais citadas

Acne	2	TP03 e TP116
Grupo sanguíneo	2	TP06 e TP12
Cintura-Quadril	2	TP06 e TP116
Colesterol total	2	TP07 e TP114
LDL	2	TP07 e TP114
HCG	2	TP08 e TP116
Testosterona	2	TP05 e TP07
Frequência respiratória	2	TP06 e TP116
HDL	2	TP07 e TP114
Triglicérides	2	TP07 e TP114
Prolactina	2	TP12 e TP114
Hipertensão	2	TP114 e TP120
Taxa de pulso	2	TP12 e TP116
Pressão arterial em repouso	1	TP10
Ultrassonografia dos ovários	1	TP115
Dados de pulso	1	TP118
Duração do Período Menstrual	1	TP03
Excesso de peso	1	TP03
Mudança de humor	1	TP03
Cansaço	1	TP03
Estradiol	1	TP07
CG	1	TP08
CP	1	TP10
Ultrassonografia do útero	1	TP11
RR	1	TP12
RCQ	1	TP12
TGF γ 1	1	TP114
IFN γ	1	TP114
IL6	1	TP114
IL10	1	TP114
PCSK9	1	TP114
Haptoglobina	1	TP114
TNF	1	TP114
PAI-1	1	TP114
IR	1	TP114
Célula MP derivada de leucócitos	1	TP114
Célula MP derivada do fator tecidual	1	TP114
Célula MP derivada de plaquetas	1	TP114
Célula MP derivada do endotélio	1	TP114
VCAM-1	1	TP114
PCSK9	1	TP114
GO	1	TP114
PCR	1	TP114
17-OH progesterona	1	TP114
D-dímero	1	TP114
Circunferência abdominal	1	TP114

COLO	1	TP114
Dislipidemia	1	TP114
Trombose	1	TP114
Diabetes mellitus	1	TP114
Fumante	1	TP114
Uso de álcool	1	TP114
Sedentário	1	TP114
Acantose nigricans	1	TP114
Hirsutismo	1	TP114
Folículos antrais no ovário esquerdo	1	TP116
Folículos antrais no ovário direito	1	TP116
Nível de hemoglobina glicada	1	TP116
PRGch	1	TP116
Casado	1	TP116
Tireotropina	1	TP116
Estado de casamento	1	TP08
ES	1	TP12
Folículo Não.	1	TP04
Média Tamanho do folículo	1	TP08
Dados da língua	1	TP118
Histórico familiar de diabetes	1	TP120
Histórico familiar de hipertensão	1	TP120
Hábitos alimentares	1	TP120
Sono	1	TP120
Ansiedade	1	TP120
Depressão	1	TP120
Insatisfação com o próprio corpo	1	TP120
Fobia social	1	TP120